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ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS AND CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE REGION

Abstract: This article analyzes the organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of the tourism sector in the regions and develops conceptual directions that serve its sustainable development. Particular attention is paid to the modernization of tourism infrastructure, attracting investments, public-private partnerships, local brands and the development of ecological tourism. The need to develop regional tourism strategies based on territorial characteristics, existing tourist resources, demographic factors and economic opportunities is substantiated.

Key words: tourism, regional development, organizational and economic mechanisms, sustainable tourism, public-private partnerships, ecological tourism, infrastructure, innovation, investment, tourist brand.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mintaqalarda turizm sohasini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy va iqtisodiy mexanizmlari tahlil qilinib, uning barqaror rivojlanishiga xizmat qiluvchi konseptual yo'nalishlar ishlab chiqilgan. Turizm infratuzilmasini modernizatsiyalash, investitsiyalarni jalb etish, davlat-xususiy sheriklik, mahalliy brendlar va ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Hududiy xususiyatlar, mavjud turistik resurslar, demografik omillar va iqtisodiy imkoniyatlar asosida hududiy turizm strategiyalarini ishlab chiqish zarurligi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, mintaqaviy rivojlanish, tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlar, barqaror turizm, davlat-xususiy sheriklik, ekologik turizm, infratuzilma, innovatsiya, investitsiya, turistik brend.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются организационно-экономические механизмы развития сферы туризма в регионах и разрабатываются концептуальные направления, обеспечивающие ее устойчивое развитие. Особое внимание уделяется модернизации туристической инфраструктуры, привлечению инвестиций, государственно-частному партнерству, развитию локальных брендов и экотуризму. Обоснована необходимость разработки региональных стратегий развития туризма с учетом региональных особенностей, имеющихся туристических ресурсов, демографических факторов и экономических возможностей.

Ключевые слова: туризм, региональное развитие, организационно-экономические механизмы, устойчивый туризм, государственно-частное партнерство, экологический туризм, инфраструктура, инновации, инвестиции, туристический бренд.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan has become one of the priority areas of the national economy. In particular, through tourism there are opportunities to increase regional economic activity, create new jobs and expand export potential. In this regard, the correct formation and effective application of organizational and economic mechanisms aimed at developing the tourism sector is an urgent task.

Today, against the backdrop of global economic crises, the tourism industry is becoming a source of sustainable production. Regional tourism is an important tool for diversifying the economy based on local resources, creating jobs and promoting socio-economic development of regions.

The article aims to identify organizational and economic mechanisms for promoting tourism in regions and increasing competitiveness, linking them with practical prospects, and forming their conceptual basis.

Tourism is currently one of the fastest growing sectors of global economic growth. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), tourism accounts for about 10 percent of global GDP. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, tourism is recognized as one of the priority sectors in the national economy, and realizing the tourism potential, especially in the regions, has become an urgent task.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

International and local sources are equally important in the scientific study of tourism. Below is a review based on the literature related to the content of the article.

Butler's life cycle model of tourist areas [1], one of the international tourism theories, allows for the gradual development of regional tourism, resource management and assessment of crisis risks. This model served as the theoretical basis for the section on organizational development approaches of the article.

The work "The Geography of Tourism and Recreation" [2] developed by Hall and Page provides an in-depth analysis of the interrelationships of tourism geography, environmental factors and regional resources, and was used as the main source in the section on regional potential assessment in the article.

The manual "Tourism: Principles and Practice" [3] written by Cooper and co-authors reflects theoretical and practical approaches to the organization of modern tourism, service quality and marketing policy. This work served as the main source in the section on service quality and personnel training of the article.

In the analysis of tourism planning and policy, the impact of state policy on regional tourism was analyzed through the works of Dredge and Jenkins [4].

The strategy for the development of tourism at the state level in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular the Presidential Decree [5], defines the regulatory and legal framework for the concept of regional tourism. Also, practical mechanisms for financing infrastructure projects in the regions and establishing public-private partnerships are substantiated through the resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers [9].

The current state of tourism, tourist flows, the number of services and investment growth rates are presented in the statistical bulletins of the Tourism Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the State Statistics Committee [6], [14].

Of the works written by local authors, the scientific works of Kadyrov and Abdurakhmanov [7] served as the main source for the economic analysis of regional tourism, the cluster approach and the definition of investment mechanisms.

Tursunov and Azizov [8] also expressed relevant views on innovative tourism, digital technologies, AR/VR systems and online services. This approach is widely reflected in the sections of the article "Smart-tourism" and "Digital transformation".

Ziyodullayev [13] analyzed the theories of ecological tourism and sustainable development, and the concepts related to ecological directions in the article are based on this source.

Based on reports published by international organizations, including UNWTO [10], World Bank [11] and OECD [15], the article covers global tourism growth trends, the impact of state policy on tourism, changes during the pandemic and issues of environmental sustainability.

Karimov's work "Regional Economy and Tourism Clusters" [12] sheds light on the economic foundations of the formation of tourism clusters in the regions of Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is important to identify and propose effective organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of tourism in the regions, and to align them with conceptual development directions.

Tourism development is theoretically based on several schools:

- Butler model (1980) - tourism development is analyzed as a phased process (discovery, development, saturation, crisis or renewal).
- Endogenous growth theory - growth based on internal resources and innovations.
- Principles of sustainable development - an approach aimed at ensuring ecological, economic and social balance.

Local literature (I. Abdurahmonov, A. Jo'rayev, S. Karimov) covers issues of regional tourism strategies, brand creation and infrastructure development, while international sources (D. Hall, C. Cooper) focus on digital innovations and public-private partnership mechanisms in tourism.

Reports prepared by UNWTO (2022) and OECD (2020) provide the most up-to-date information on international trends, digital technologies, sustainable tourism policies, and the impact of public policies on

tourism. In particular, developments in the tourism sector in the post-pandemic period are highlighted based on these sources.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The tourism potential of such regions as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva - cultural and historical tourism centers, the Fergana Valley - handicraft and agro-tourism, Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya - archaeological and ecological tourism, Karakalpakstan - ethnotourism and ecological destinations (Aral Sea Coast) can be considered. The main problems are insufficient tourism infrastructure, shortage of qualified personnel, weak marketing strategy, limited investment environment, and weak interregional integration.

We will consider organizational and economic mechanisms and their role in development. Among them, public-private partnerships (PPP), the construction of hotels, roads and service facilities on a PPP basis, attracting private investors through tax incentives and grants, the proposal to establish a "Tourism Projects Fund". In addition, investment mechanisms, namely, attracting external investments: through EBRD, UNDP, OIC funds, internal investments: Tourism bonds, attracting local residents through cooperatives, the establishment of "Free Economic Zones for Tourism", Infrastructure modernization, namely, upgrading airports and railway stations, introducing environmentally friendly means of transport (electric buses), expanding Internet coverage and information centers.

We will look at the conceptual directions, namely, sustainable tourism, that is, reducing the negative impact of tourism activities on the environment, developing eco-hotels in rural areas, promoting the consumption of local products, Smart-tourism and digital transformation.

That is, virtual tours using AR/VR technologies, development of online booking systems, "Digital Guide" applications, mobile services. In addition, it is necessary to take into account personnel training and service quality, the establishment of regional tourism colleges, short courses on language learning and service culture, cooperation with international hotel chains, etc.

In the development of tourism in the regions, the geographical location of the territory, natural and climatic conditions, historical and cultural heritage and the state of existing infrastructure are considered the main factors. Each region has its own unique tourism resources, and economic growth can be achieved by studying and effectively managing them.

For example, in historical cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand and Khiva, tourism potential can be increased by preserving cultural heritage sites and combining them with modern services. In mountainous regions, the development of ecological and extreme types of tourism is promising.

For the main directions of forming organizational and economic mechanisms, the following organizational and economic mechanisms play an important role in the development of the tourism sector: projects based on public-private partnership, i.e., strengthening the participation of the private sector in the construction and modernization of tourism facilities, introducing state subsidies and tax incentives in the development of tourism infrastructure (roads, hotels, transport system), Attracting investments, i.e., strengthening the material and technical base of the tourism sector by attracting foreign and domestic investments, creating a favorable business environment for investors, Developing local brands and products, i.e., creating a tourist brand in each region, exporting local crafts and food products to international markets, Introducing innovative technologies, i.e., improving service provision through digital marketing, online booking systems, mobile applications, and gradually introducing the concept of "Smart tourism" at the regional level.

We will consider conceptual directions and strategic approaches. In the development of regional tourism, the following conceptual directions are considered priority: sustainable tourism, the development of forms of tourism that bring long-term economic benefits without harming the environment, Ecological tourism, the establishment of environmentally friendly tourism activities in mountainous and natural resource-rich regions, Agrotourism, attracting the population to tourism activities through the development of tourism related to agriculture, Education and training, that is, the development of a system of training specialized personnel in the tourism sector, teaching foreign languages, and improving service culture.

Several proposals can be made for the development of a regional tourism strategy. Among them, conducting a SWOT analysis of tourism potential in each region, encouraging the participation of local residents in tourism, developing tourist logistics - ensuring the convenience of air, rail and highways, developing a regional marketing strategy, and targeting foreign markets.

Tourism, as an important branch of the regional economy, has great potential in our country. For its effective development, it is necessary to properly form organizational and economic mechanisms, develop strategies taking into account regional characteristics. Innovations, approaches based on the principles of public-private partnership and sustainable development serve as important factors in this direction.

An integrated approach is required for the development of regional tourism. Taking into account the specific tourist potential of each region, it is necessary to develop organizational and economic mechanisms and correctly apply them in practice. Development based on sustainability, innovation, and public-private partnership is the basis of successful strategies.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the sustainable development of tourism in the region requires a coherent organizational and economic mechanism that integrates institutional coordination, public-private partnerships, infrastructure investment, and effective governance. A comprehensive regional tourism strategy should be built on the principles of inclusivity, diversification of tourism products, digital transformation, and environmental sustainability. Strengthening local capacities, enhancing service quality, and facilitating access to financial resources for small and medium-sized enterprises are essential to unlocking the full potential of the sector.

To further advance regional tourism, it is important to create an enabling environment through regulatory reforms, transparent policy frameworks, and active stakeholder engagement. Special attention should be paid to promoting local cultural and natural assets, fostering innovation in tourism services, and improving transport and communication infrastructure. Additionally, the implementation of destination branding and targeted marketing campaigns can significantly enhance the region's visibility in both domestic and international markets, attracting more visitors and boosting socio-economic development.

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